

LEGAL IN YOUTH IN ENSURING HUMAN DIGNITY EXALTATION
OF CONSCIOUSNESS AND CULTURE

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Abstract. When we reflect on the changes that have occurred in the life of the country, we witness that in the fertile ground of independence, the value of human being is glorified in our country, especially we are creating wide opportunities for young people, and we are focused on ensuring human rights and freedoms. There is great wisdom in the saying of our grandfather Amir Temur, "Where there is rule of law, there is freedom." This wisdom has its own meaning even now.

Keywords: "a society where human dignity is a priority, a people-loving state, "For human dignity".

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has such lines in the main Constitution, "in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the supremacy of laws are recognized without words. The state, its bodies, officials, public associations and Citizens Act in accordance with the Constitution and laws." Raising legal consciousness and culture in young people in order to ensure human value in the country is one of the most important conditions for ensuring the rule of law and strengthening legality. A number of problems and shortcomings have been preserved that prevent young people from forming an attitude of respect for Human Rights and freedoms, raising their legal consciousness and culture, increasing the level of their legal literacy in society. The whole society is responsible for the formation of legal immunity in relation to factors that negatively affect the legal education of young people, respect for laws and rules of conduct in each person, as well as in representatives of the younger generation, loyalty to national values, and the thought of a sense of impurity in relation to offenders. In recent ears, significant work has been carried out on the radical reform of the national legal system in ensuring human value in society, raising the legal consciousness and culture of young people, as well as training qualified legal personnel. Insufficient knowledge of young people in order to increase their legal consciousness and culture, their legal knowledge in ensuring human dignity, as well as practically

not using the opportunity to appeal to the court over illegal decisions of state bodies, are the reason for the emergence of cases of discrimination of young people's rights and legitimate interests by officials.

In order to ensure human dignity, it is necessary to further improve the effectiveness of work on raising the legal consciousness and culture of representatives of the younger generation, to introduce modern methods of increasing the legal knowledge of citizens in harmony with socio-political changes, as well as to form a strong legal immunity of the population, especially young people, to protect. At the same time, the legal consciousness and legal culture of the people of the younger generation indicate that they treat legal norms with respect, and not just a simple attitude towards this right. Respect for the law, its norms and their full-fledged work presupposes that everyone is equal before them. Although the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees that human and citizen are equal rights in this regard, various offenses are still committed in the country by our citizens and young people, employees of state and public administration bodies, as a result of which they have not et realized their rights correctly and completely. Unfortunately, this phenomenon can be observed among both young people, both young adults, both women and both men. To this end, it should be said that it is necessary to raise and develop the legal consciousness and legal culture of young people, to form the skills of legal culture in them as much as water and air. Today's young people tend to follow democratic values. Among them, the mood of feeling like a citizen of Uzbekistan is strongly manifested. This suggests that a lot of work has been done to elevate their legal consciousness and culture, and finds expression in the minds and behavior of young people. At all times, representatives of the younger generation wanted the consciousness and culture of members of society to be developed, progressive, creative, progressive, and for this purpose, a sense of respect for legal norms and laws of youth was formed, and this process was considered one of the main tasks.

In ensuring human dignity, citizens, as well as young people, always feel their responsibility for their bloodthirsty, belonging to the multinational country of Uzbekistan in order to raise their legal consciousness and culture. At each age of the country, the formation of legal consciousness and culture, the formation of a civic sense and worldview are important political, social, moral, cultural significance. The highest goal is to glorify the dignity of a person, his honor and dignity. That is why the exaltation of the legal consciousness and culture of young people in ensuring human value in our country constitutes their

awareness and willingness to protect their rights and freedoms. In this case, he should first of all rely on the foundations of the Constitution and legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the level of legal consciousness and the rise of mediocrity in young people is determined not by the number of laws adopted, but by the full implementation of these laws. In this important work, it is of particular importance to educate in youth a sense of respect for laws, regulatory documents. In this case, understanding in the minds of representatives of the younger generation what is good, what is bad, what is possible and what is not, the concepts of law and duty, honesty and purity on the basis of norms of morality, and teaching the most important principles in our headcount from childhood in simple language will pay off in the future. At this point, it is worth mentioning a comment. Today, laws should be developed in a simple language that is understood by ordinary people, representatives of the younger generation. In order to raise the legal consciousness and culture of young people in ensuring human dignity on all fronts in independent Uzbekistan, we must not forget that the effective and efficient use of all forms and methods of legal education in the responsible circuit, which is undergoing radical changes, is of great importance. It is impossible to achieve the rule of law, progress by teaching the youth of modern times only laws and intimidation with responsibility. As noted above, it is no secret that many decisions, laws are being issued for the younger generation. The law "on state youth policy" adopted by the legislative chamber on August 12, 2016 consists of 4 chapters, 33 articles, in which state youth policy is a system of economic, social, organizational, legal measures to be implemented by the state and to form youth socially, to raise their legal consciousness and culture, to create conditions for the development of Article 5 of this law specifically states that "ensuring the rights, freedoms and legitimate mafaates of young people elevate the level of legal consciousness and culture of young people." Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2019 no PF-5618 "on measures to radically improve the system of raising legal consciousness and culture in society", which was developed in order to raise the legal consciousness and culture of young people in the country, to increase their legal knowledge in harmony with socio-political changes, to, it was adopted to widely promote the ideas of maintaining a balance between personal interests and the interests of society, to teach them the important and necessary aspects of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to teach patriotism, history, religion, national values of our people, as well as to raise the legal consciousness and culture of young people in

ensuring human At this point, it is natural that the question of what is legal consciousness and legal culture itself is defamed. Legal consciousness, in short, refers to the attitude of people regarding law and legislation towards the right, whose feelings arise under the influence of practical experiences. Legal culture refers to the fact that citizens acquire important knowledge of the state and law, be able to interpret their understanding of the current normative legal acts and be able to make the right profit from them. From the path of society, the path of democracy, the rapid development and understanding of the essence of the reforms carried out in this regard, participation in this process necessitates a high level of legal consciousness and culture of young people. Each member of society must thoroughly know his rights and duties and responsibilities, take it as a vital need, the worldview, thinking of citizens, as well as young people, changes in accordance with the life of the country, updates are closely related to legal consciousness and legal culture in ensuring human value. It should be noted that legal culture refers to the level of legal literacy of young people, respect for laws, the execution of legal norms, the ability to practice Hayat, intolerance to offenders, legal activity and initiative, and in this regard it is necessary to give young people a head start from one collar to raise legal awareness and legal culture in ensuring human

In conclusion, it should be noted again that the key to perfection lies in the achievement of heights in the legal consciousness and culture of young people in ensuring human value. It is not for nothing that great attention is paid to the upbringing of young people as people with knowledge and high spirituality in the country. The more people with a high legal culture in independent Uzbekistan, the easier it is to achieve the rule of law.

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